

NATIONAL COUNCIL OF RESEARCH

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

The mechanisms put in place by Italian legislation¹ to combat harassment and promote equal opportunities in public workplaces, including academia, have seen their role slightly strengthened. Some universities and research organisations have also shared experiences in addressing the issue. The requirement to introduce Codes of Conduct that specifically refer to sexual harassment and to setting up a protection system involving the Guarantee Committee of Equal Opportunities (CUG)² and the confidential counsellor³ has helped to increase awareness of gender-based violence (GBV) and has ushered in concrete tools to fight the phenomenon. However, the lack of specific guidelines on how to draw up a Code of Conduct and to implement it in practice, without any independent body with control and coordinate functions, has resulted in a highly differentiated system of protection (Perini 2019). Another weakness has been the tendency to focus on the issue of gender equality rather than on GBV, minimising the gender component in addressing issues such as sexual harassment and gender discrimination. This has produced a formalised and technical approach and reduced the overall effectiveness of the system. Even though most Italian universities have introduced Codes of Conduct regarding harassment, there has never been any formal action taken against universities that have not yet complied with the national legislation, despite the fact that the Italian law provides for the possibility of sanctioning organisations that fail to do so. It is hard to estimate how many higher education institutions and research funding organisations in Italy have failed to comply with national regulations, since there is no specific body that can gather such data at the national level. As of December 2020, only 32 of 85 universities had instituted the position of a confidential counsellor within their protection system.⁴

¹ Legislative Decree No. 198/2006, Code of Equal Opportunities in the Workplace.

² A formal body with proposing, consulting, and verification functions for the development of a culture of equal opportunities and against discrimination.

³ The confidential counsellor helps victims of discrimination and harassment and, at the request of the person concerned, takes on the case and informs them of the most suitable way of dealing with it.

⁴ <https://www.visir.is/g/20171884043d>

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

The reference policy is the Code for the Prevention and the Fight against Harassment in the CNR (2020) which specifically addresses sexual and gender-based harassment.⁵ The main actor is the **CNR CUG**, a joint body appointed by the administration and by trade unions, which collaborates with other CNR internal offices: the Independent Body of Evaluation⁶ and the Office for Training.⁷ In addition, within the CNR administrative framework, the Department of Prevention and Protection⁸, the Department of Disciplinary Proceedings and Integrity⁹ and the facility managers are responsible for defining what measures to take in the event of harassment and how to raise awareness and train employees. Directive No. 2/2019 of the Ministry of Public Administration also assigns a prominent role to the CUG which can be invited by victims to express its opinion on the cases of violence, harassment and discrimination.

The Prevention Code states that gender relations and the inequality of power between men and women are central to understanding the deep roots of sexual harassment. It defines a set of formal and informal procedures for reporting and taking action to eliminate discriminatory behaviours. The Prevention Code is already effective for reporting and activating disciplinary measures (it is the Disciplinary Proceedings Office that ascertains incidents and takes measures to resolve such situations). Due to changes in the top management of the CNR, however, the confidential counsellor has not yet been appointed. However, the procedure for appointing the counsellor and setting up the helpdesk have been initiated.

URL

- › Code for the Prevention and the Fight against Harassment in the CNR: <https://viva.cnr.it/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/codice-per-prevenzione-ontrasto-delle-molestie-nel-cnr-luglio-2020.pdf>

Entry into force: 2020

TRAINING

The Report on the Triennial Plan for Training 2019-2021¹⁰ states that in 2016 there were two mandatory courses for managers and staff to raise awareness of gender issues and to make known the Code of Conduct and the current laws on harassment. However, these courses never took place because the person who proposed them became unexpectedly unavailable.

⁵ Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche. (2020). Codice per la prevenzione e il contrasto delle molestie nel CNR.

⁶ Organismo Indipendente di Valutazione (OIV) which draws up comprehensive surveys on the perceived well-being of CNR workers and collaborates with the institute's CUG to define the overall picture in terms of harassment and discrimination, considered as one element among others (i.e. sense of belonging, relational climate) that influences the well-being of workers. To date, two inquiries have been carried out: 2012-2013; 2014-2015.

⁷ Unità Formazione e Welfare which organises the annual training plan for personnel, organising training courses. Specifically, the adoption of training courses for staff on the phenomenon of sexual harassment and the dissemination of knowledge of the Code adopted by the CNR, should be achieved through the direct collaboration of this office with the CUG. However, at the moment, the courses have only been planned and never initiated.

⁸ Unità di Prevenzione e Protezione.

⁹ Unità Procedimenti Disciplinari e Integrità.

¹⁰ Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche. (2019). Piano Triennale della formazione 2019-2021.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

CRN plays a prominent role in providing knowledge about GBV in Italy. The Institute for Research on Population and Social Policies (IRPPS)¹¹, in collaboration with the Department of Equal Opportunities and the National Institute of Statistics (ISTAT),¹² developed the VIVA project with the aim of monitoring and analysing the policies on and provision of services on GBV.¹³ The project comprises two complementary studies. The first is a survey on the provision of services to women victims of violence, with the aim of defining a quantitative and qualitative picture of the Italian situation in order to design an optimal system of services. The second aims to evaluate policies and actions implemented within the framework of the National Strategic Plan on Male Violence (2017-2020). Moreover, the CNR IRPPS, under the VIVA project, has initiated a study on GBV during the pandemic, by researching the cases dealt with by 335 anti-violence centres, highlighting the critical issues in the operating procedures and in the cases that were dealt with. The IRPPS also ran two national enquiries (in March and July 2020) on the impact of the lockdown on GBV, with a focus on violence induced by conditions of stereotypes and social stress.¹⁴ The IRPPS, together with the Association Donne e Scienza, associated a conference called '#WeTooInScience, Sexual Harassment in Higher Education Institutions and Research Organisations' (2018), which represents the most comprehensive study on GBV in Italian universities.

Knowledge on GBV is also promoted within the CNR through conference initiatives and research activities organized by the CUG, trade union representatives within the CNR, and CNR institutes and departments. For example, the Institute for International Legal Studies (ISGI) produces publications and organises seminars on the execution and application of relevant GBV treaties in Italy, taking into account the jurisprudence of treaty bodies and the evaluation of relevant Italian legislation.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence:

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

¹¹ Istituto di Ricerca sulle Popolazioni e sulle Politiche Sociali.

¹² Istituto Nazionale di Statistica.

¹³ The project was part of the strategic Assistance and Promotion axis defined, under the direct influence of the Istanbul Convention, by the National Strategic Plan on Male Violence 2017-2020, which provided for direct collaboration between the Department of Equal Opportunities and IRPPS for the evaluation of policies on GBV.

¹⁴ Those studies are part of a bigger project: Social Change Observatory in the Covid-19 period.

7Ps covered: 6Ps are covered – prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, provision of services and policy.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Intersectionality addressed

Yes. Sexual orientation, race, disability and age are addressed.

Specific vulnerable groups

Not defined

Target groups

The policy covers academic staff, non-academic staff, and other e.g. companies that supply goods or services or carry out work for the CNR; employees of companies that the CNR controls or participates in.

Bystanders addressed: No.

Role of perpetrators addressed: No.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: No.

Monitoring: The number of cases and services provided to victims are monitored.

Every six months the confidential counsellor must report on their activities and the cases they have addressed to the general manager and to the central director of Resource Management, while respecting the anonymity and confidentiality of the victims in these reports. However, since the confidential counsellor has not yet been established, this requirement at present remains only on paper.

Evaluation: No.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

The policy sets a single step-by-step procedure for reporting and investigating, for all.

The policy defines: Who to contact, responsible persons / units, sanctions.

Who to contact: In an informal procedure, the Prevention Code refers to the confidential counsellor or the help desk (also managed by the confidential counsellor). However, no one has yet been appointed to fill these roles. Nevertheless, the recently approved Gender Equality Plan foresees their implementation within a short time. In an internal formal procedure, the victims should contact the head of the unit they work or study in or the Disciplinary Procedures and Integrity Unit. In an external formal procedure, on the other hand, direct contact between the victim and the competent authorities is defined through the process of a formal legal complaint.

Responsible units: Internal formal complaints are filed with the Disciplinary Procedures and Integrity Unit, which is the only office that can define binding disciplinary measures. However, the code provides for an informal procedure, and if the case can be resolved through this procedure it is possible to avoid filing a formal complaint with the Disciplinary Procedures and Integrity Unit. The confidential counsellor can propose measures (such as transferring the staff involved; warning the perpetrator; proposing joint meetings) that are defined as the first steps in resolving cases to avoid the initiation of a formal procedure.

Outcomes: In addition to the measures defined as resolution and reconciliation in the informal procedure, measures such as transferring staff to different offices and issuing a perpetrator with a warning, the text generically states that the administration will adopt organisational measures necessary for the immediate cessation of sexual harassment and discriminatory behaviours and for restoring a safe work environment with mutual respect between staff.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researcher Karla Nicole Brunello in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

